

POSSIBLE ANTI-TUBERCULAR COMPOUNDS. PART II.
PREPARATION OF ACYLDIPHENYLYLAMIDINES

BY VINAY S. MISRA AND MAHESEWARI P. KHARE

With a view to further increasing the surface area of 4-aminodiphenyl compound of known anti-tubercular activity, seven higher 4'-acyldiphenylylamidines have been prepared

In Part I this series (Misra and Khare, this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 695) a series of 4'-aceto-4-N-diphenylylamidines have been described, the starting material being 4-aminodiphenyl, a strongly anti-tubercular compound.

In the present paper we have tried to further increase the surface area of N-4-diphenylylamidines by introducing the lipoid-soluble propionyl and *n*-butyryl groups in the 4'-position of the 4-aminodiphenyl instead of the acetyl, and subsequently preparing seven new amidines by the usual method of Oxley and Short (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 147), adopted by us in the previous case.

The 4'-propio-4-aminodiphenyl was prepared by us by the application of the Friedel-Crafts reaction. The Friedel-Crafts reaction was conducted in the presence of dry carbon disulphide with 2.5 moles of anhydrous aluminium chloride when the intermediate 4'-propio-N-4-propioacetaminodiphenyl, as expected from the analogous aceto series (Misra and Khare, *loc. cit.*) was obtained in excellent yields. In the case of the butyro series, instead of the diacyl compound, 4'-butyro-N-4-acetaminodiphenyl was obtained, as confirmed by its nitrogen content and that of its 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone.

The respective free amines were liberated by the hydrolysis of the corresponding acylamines with concentrated hydrochloric acid.

The Friedel Crafts reaction was also conducted in the presence of dry nitrobenzene as in the previous paper, but in this case, contrary to our expectations, the ketone synthesis and the hydrolysis of the intermediate product proceeded simultaneously, and the free amine could only be obtained in very poor yields as a considerable amount of a tarry product was also produced.

These amines were converted into the corresponding benzene sulphonate in the manner described in the earlier communication (*loc cit.*).

These benzene sulphonates (I & II) were then fused at 220°-230° with excess of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-tolyl and *p*-aniso-nitriles respectively, and the appropriate amidine-benzene sulphonates were obtained,

The free amidines (in 28 to 68% yield) were liberated by treating the benzene sulphonates with 5*N*-sodium hydroxide and were recrystallised from chloroform and petroleum ether except the 4'-butyro-*N*-4-diphenyl-*o*-tolylamidine which, however, could not be obtained in a pure form in spite of repeated attempts.

The anti-tubercular activity of the amidines will be reported latter on.

EXPERIMENTAL

4'-Propio-N-4-propioacetaminodiphenyl (I).—Anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.5 *M*, 30 g.) was added to 4-acetaminodiphenyl (16 g.), suspended in dry CS₂ (40 g.) in a 500 c. c. R. B. flask fitted with a reflux condenser having a calcium chloride tube and a dropping funnel at its top. Now, to the cooled mixture propionyl chloride (3.5 *M*, 18 g.) was added dropwise when the reaction proceeded briskly with the evolution of gaseous HCl. After the evolution of HCl had slowed down the product was refluxed for half an hour on a water-bath to complete the reaction. The CS₂ was then distilled off and the resulting complex, a green paste, was decomposed with crushed ice and dilute HCl. The resulting yellow powder was filtered and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid, m. p. 226-27°, yield 53% of theory (12.3 g.). (Found : N, 5.0. C₂₀H₂₁O₃N requires N, 4.34 per cent).

The 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of the above was recrystallised from nitrobenzene as a red powder, m. p. 266-68°. (Found : 13.77. C₂₆H₂₅O₆N₅ requires N, 13.90 per cent).

4'-Butyro-N-4-acetaminodiphenyl (II).—Anhydrous aluminium chloride (2.5 *M*, 30 g.) was added to 4-acetaminodiphenyl (16 g.), suspended in dry CS₂ (40 g.). Butyryl chloride (3.5 *M*, 20 g.) was added dropwise under cooling. The subsequent treatments were similar to the previous compound (I). The resulting powder was filtered and recrystallised from alcohol as a yellow crystalline powder, m. p. 209°, yield 70% of theory (14 g.). (Found : N, 5.30. C₁₈H₁₉O₂N requires N, 4.98 per cent).

The 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of (II) was recrystallised from nitrobenzene as red crystals, m. p. 262-63°. (Found : N, 15.30. C₂₄H₂₃O₅N₅ requires N, 15.19 per cent).

4'-Propio-4-aminodiphenyl (III).—4'-Propio-*N*-4-propioacetaminodiphenyl (12.3 g.) was hydrolysed with HCl (conc., 50 c. c.) by refluxing for four hours and the product neutralised with concentrated ammonia when a yellow mass was obtained. This on recrystallisation from 80% alcohol gave a yellow amorphous powder, m. p. 168-69°, yield 93% of theory (8 g.). (Found : N, 5.70. C₁₅H₁₅ON requires N, 6.22 per cent).

The 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of (III) was recrystallised from nitrobenzene as red powder, m. p. 231-32°. (Found : N, 16.93. C₂₁H₁₉O₄N₅ requires N, 17.28 per cent).

4'-Butyro-4-aminodiphenyl (IV).—*4'-Butyro-N-4-acetaminodiphenyl* (14 g.) was hydrolysed with HCl (50 c. c., conc.) and neutralised with ammonia (conc.). The precipitated powder was recrystallised from alcohol as brown needles, m. p. 116-17°, yield 94% of theory (9 g.). (Found : N, 6.15. $C_{16}H_{17}ON$ requires N, 5.86 per cent).

The *2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* of (IV) was recrystallised from nitrobenzene as a red shining crystals, m. p. 253°. (Found : N, 17.10. $C_{22}H_{21}O_4N_6$ requires N, 16.71 per cent).

4'-Propio-4-diphenylammonium-benzene sulphonate (A).—*4'-Propio-4-aminodiphenyl* (1 M, 7 g.) was stirred mechanically in 200 c. c. of dry ether and benzene sulphonic acid (1 M, 5 g.), dissolved in 10 c. c. of methyl alcohol, was added slowly. A white paste was formed which was filtered and recrystallised from hot water as a pale yellow powder, m. p. 244-46°, yield 42% of theory (5 g.). (Found : N, 4.10. $C_{21}H_{21}O_4NS$ requires N, 3.65 per cent).

4'-Butyro-4-diphenylammonium-benzene sulphonate (B).—To *4'-butyro-4-aminodiphenyl* (1 M, 8 g.) stirred in 200 c. c. dry ether, benzene sulphonic acid (1 M, 5 g.), dissolved in methyl alcohol, was added dropwise. The benzene sulphonate separated out and was filtered and recrystallised from 30% alcohol as a white amorphous powder, m. p. 257-60°, yield 68% of theory (9 g.). (Found : N, 3.76. $C_{22}H_{23}O_4NS$ requires N, 3.52 per cent).

*4'-Propio-N-4-diphenyl-*o*-tolylamidine*.—The compound (A) (2.5 g.) was mixed with *o*-tolyl nitrile (2.5 g.) in a 100 c. c. flask fitted with a reflux condenser and a gas absorption tower. The mixture was heated at 220°-230° (external bath temperature) for 4 hours. The pasty product formed was triturated with ether and a yellow amorphous powder of amidinebenzene sulphonate was obtained which was then stirred mechanically in 100 c. c. of 5*N*-NaOH for 6 hours and filtered. The resultant amidine was then recrystallised from chloroform and petroleum ether to give a dark brown solid, m. p. 125-30°, yield 59% of theory (1.3 g.). (Found : N, 7.70. $C_{23}H_{22}ON_2$ requires N, 8.18 per cent).

*4'-Propio-N-4-diphenyl-*m*-tolylamidine*.—The compound (A) (2 g.) was heated with *m*-tolyl nitrile (2 g., excess) for 4 hours at 220°-230°. The amidine was liberated as above as a yellow amorphous powder, m. p. 175-79°, yield 28% of theory (0.5 g.). (Found : N, 7.61. $C_{23}H_{22}ON_2$ requires N, 8.18 per cent).

*4'-Propio-N-4-diphenyl-*p*-tolylamidine* was obtained by refluxing the mixture of (A) (2.5 g.) and *p*-tolyl nitrile (4 g.) at 220°-225° for 6 hours as a yellow powder, m. p. 178-82°, yield 40% of theory (0.9 g.). (Found : N, 7.55. $C_{23}H_{22}ON_2$ requires N, 8.18 per cent).

*4'-Propio-N-4-diphenyl-*p*-anisoylamidine* was similarly obtained as above by heating (A) (2.5 g.) with *p*-anisonitrile (5 g., excess) at 230° for 4 hours, m. p. 180°-82°, yield 43% of theory. (1 g.). (Found : N, 7.30. $C_{23}H_{22}O_2N_2$ requires N, 7.81 per cent).

*4'-Butyro-N-4-diphenyl-*m*-tolylamidine.*—The compound (B) (2.5 g.) was heated with *m*-tolyl nitrile (3 g.) for 4 hours at 230° under reflux. The amidine was obtained as a brown solid in the usual manner, m. p. 148-53°, yield 68% of theory (1.5 g.). (Found : N, 7.25. $C_{24}H_{24}ON_2$ requires N, 7.86 per cent).

*4'-Butyro-N-4-diphenyl-*p*-tolylamidine* was similarly obtained by heating from (B, 2.5 g.) and *p*-tolyl nitrile (3 g.) at 220° for 4 hours as a yellow amorphous powder, m. p. 181-85°, yield 54% of theory (1.2 g.). (Found : N, 7.65. $C_{24}H_{24}ON_2$ requires N, 7.86 per cent).

*4'-Butyro-N-4-diphenyl-*p*-anisoylamidine.*—The compound (B) (2.5 g.) was mixed with *p*-anisonitrile (3.5 g.) and heated at 230° for 5 hours. The yellow amorphous amidine was liberated in the usual manner and melted at 156-60°, yield 42% of theory (1.4 g.). (Found : 7.75. $C_{24}H_{24}O_2N_2$ requires N, 7.53 per cent).

The authors are thankful to Dr. A. B. Sen for his kind interest in the present work.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
ORGANIC BRANCH,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY, LUCKNOW.

Received July 14, 1952.